

Setting the stage for a 'different conversation' about open access

Foreword

The Open Access Scholarly Publishing Association (OASPA) is launching a new project for 2025, bringing together publishing organisations with those who pay for, fund and invest in scholarly communication. This initiative, delivered in collaboration with Research Consulting, builds on OASPA's research and outputs of the past few years, following over 3,000 downloads of these recommendations on financial and workflow barriers.

In a recent article, we addressed the importance of asking the right questions to complete the transition to open access, urging stakeholders from across the ecosystem to participate in an ongoing process of evolution and course correction. We point to the need for a 'different conversation' to take the transition to open access forward. This conversation is the focus of this project primer, which is meant as a catalyst for cross-sector dialogue and a framework for reimagining how we collectively advance open access in the coming years.

Accompanying the release of this project primer is a feedback survey open to anyone with an interest in the transition to open access; in addition, over sixty participants across six continents have been invited to a set of multi-stakeholder workshops. Through these mechanisms, we aim to explore diverse routes to open access, their contributions to date and the roles they may play in continuing the global transition to open access. We will acknowledge and actively engage publishing organisations across a variety of models and disciplines, many already fully open access, as well as libraries, consortia and funders

who pay for, support and invest in publishing. The idea of a 'Next 50%' (the title of our project) refers to the percentage of peer-reviewed journal articles and conference papers that are available via open access either on a publisher platform or by other routes. This does not reflect a broad definition of openness, which would include more output types (e.g. books) and emerging output types that, for some disciplines, are part of the same picture (e.g. preprint posting, registered reports).

The 50% figure also masks other barriers to engaging with open access publishing, such as the financial means to support fee-based open access publication or the predominance of the English language in scholarly outputs.

This document is intended to frame the issues and takes you through three aspects of openness that need to be combined to provide a truly equitable system. At the end, we pose several questions that we would like readers to carefully consider prior to attending project workshops or providing feedback via our open survey. Our goal is to help stakeholders across the scholarly publishing community embrace a more inclusive vision of open access - one that distributes benefits and responsibilities fairly, based on collectively determined priorities.

Claire Redhead, Executive Director, OASPA

Achieving truly global open access

The open access landscape already features multiple pathways: journals using article processing charges; transformative agreements like Read & Publish deals; collective funding models such as Subscribe to Open; no-fee open access supported by grants, societies, or libraries; and other open publishing infrastructures serving different communities. Each model alone is unlikely to be enough to complete the transition, and the models to support and sustain a fully open access future across a diversity of publishing organisations most likely have not yet been created. We believe that the scholarly community should take responsibility for improving the current mix of business models while, at the same time, working toward new ones that transcend the status quo. Our goal in this project is to have a thoughtful, forward-looking discussion that is less charged and more inclusive about what open really means in scholarly communication. The emphasis is on stimulating new ways to think about and progress towards open access, rather than rehashing long-running debates where we already know stakeholders disagree.

To inform our discussion, we are using a framework by [Pinfield \(2024\)](#), which proposes that truly equitable global open access requires three interconnected forms of openness (Figure 1). **Scientific openness** refers to a largely Western and market-led understanding of open access: making articles, books and other outputs digital, online, available free of charge and free of most copyright and licensing restrictions. **Participatory openness** focuses on involving more diverse communities: this addresses the cultural and economic factors that allow people from different contexts and regions to contribute to scientific knowledge and meaningfully engage in exchange of ideas. Openness should not passively remove barriers but actively transform global knowledge systems. Finally, **epistemic openness** expands the above by advocating for a wider and more inclusive understanding of what constitutes valid and valuable knowledge. This recognises that legitimate knowledge extends beyond Western scientific traditions and includes diverse knowledge systems from around the world.

Figure 1. Framework for a global open access transition (Pinfield, 2024)

Scientific openness

Making content freely and openly available for all to read and re-use

A large proportion of outputs are freely available online but progress appears to be slowing down

For over two decades, we have been experiencing increasing levels of open access and have made remarkable progress, reaching almost 60% of open access for articles, reviews and conference papers as of 2023 (Figure 2, not considering the Bronze route). It is important to appreciate the scale of this phenomenon:

- the above percentage is a share of over 4.4m articles, reviews and conference papers published within 2023 alone, of which over 2.6m are available via open access via the Gold, Hybrid and Green routes;
- the number of articles, reviews and conference papers published annually has grown significantly over time, starting from just above 1.1m in 2003;
- between 2003 and 2023, over 20.3m articles, reviews and conference papers have been published via the Gold, Hybrid and Green routes; in the same period, over 24.3m articles, reviews and conference papers were published via the subscription route.

The data shown in Figure 2 - which remains an incomplete picture of global output - suggests that the growth in open access publishing may be slowing down in percentage terms. This, combined with the fact that the proportion of subscription content appears to be plateauing after consistently declining for almost 20 years, suggests that the scholarly publishing community should reflect on its current trajectory if the goal remains to make most published outputs available via open access.

The picture for long-form outputs is rather different, including due to data being significantly more patchy. Based on Dimensions data, only about 18% of monographs and books are available via the Gold, Hybrid and Green routes for the year 2023. This corresponds to almost 19,000 of these items, out of a total of just above 108,000. This is a helpful reminder that pursuing open access does not mean achieving a single target or measure, but engaging a diverse mix of stakeholders across disciplines that have different publishing customs, as well as considering a range of policy landscapes and socio-economic factors across the world.

Figure 2. Percentage of articles, reviews and conference papers by open access route (data sourced from Dimensions, an inter-linked research information system provided by Digital Science - <https://www.dimensions.ai>)

Scientific openness

Making content freely and openly available for all to read and re-use

North-South disparities continue to affect where knowledge is accessed and produced

Thinking about open access in terms of what percentage of published literature is openly available, as opposed to subscription-only, provides an incomplete understanding of the landscape. Indeed, previous research shows that greater access to published content does not necessarily reduce inequities in knowledge production:

“Despite the efforts of Research4Life and similar initiatives, [...] the contribution made by researchers in its eligible countries as authors, editors and peer reviewers remains low.” [Powell et al., 2020](#)

Furthermore, open access alone cannot address research infrastructure disparities, such as unreliable internet connectivity, outdated technology or limited technical support. Even when academic literature is technically “open,” practical barriers can prevent meaningful access and participation.

Broader socio-economic trends also contribute to this picture, starting from the fact that research agendas are shaped by wealthier funders and nations. This mismatch leads to situations where scholarly works may be available via open access but not be relevant or tailored to the contexts or phenomena that researchers in low-resource settings may wish to study.

Full availability encompasses both reading and reuse permissions

While basic access to read content is essential, true open scholarship requires permissions to reuse, redistribute and build upon existing work. The spectrum of open licences represents different stakeholder priorities regarding commercialisation, integrity and attribution. Publishers, authors and funders often have divergent preferences, with some funders mandating CC BY while some authors and other actors prefer more restrictive options that limit commercial reuse or adaptations.

In previous years, researchers and institutions sought not just access to read scholarly works, but also the right to computationally analyse large corpora of academic literature through text and data mining (TDM). While some jurisdictions have introduced TDM exceptions to copyright law, these provisions vary significantly across regions, creating a fragmented global environment for computational research. The question of whether open access materials should automatically grant TDM rights remains contentious, with some publishers developing [separate licensing approaches](#) specifically for computational access.

The emergence of generative artificial intelligence has introduced a more complex discussion at the interface between copyright, scholarly publishing and technological innovation, creating new tensions. A [recent blog post](#) reflects on the implications of a licence that enables open access for readers also enabling the materials to be used for the training of large language models.

This is a rapidly developing area, requiring engagement from all stakeholders involved and further reflection on the potential implications on a fair transition to open access.

“Generative AI raises profound questions regarding the foundational assumptions that underpin copyright law, one of the most pressing of which concerns the data used to train generative AI models.” [Buick, 2024](#)

In practice, generative artificial intelligence is transforming a movement focused on increasing access for human readers into a complex socio-technical challenge with associated commercial implications. Moving forward, the open access community faces the delicate task of preserving the core values of scientific openness while adapting to a rapidly changing landscape of technologies and tools. This will require not just technical or legal solutions, but in-depth discussion about the ethical dimensions of knowledge creation and dissemination in an era where the boundaries between human and machine-generated content continue to blur.

Participatory openness

Enabling diverse contributions to and engagement in research from a wide range of actors

A breadth of business models support open access publication, each with benefits and challenges

To develop a successful, long-term approach to equitable open access, we must recognise and consider a range of business models.

Article processing charge-based models have allowed some publishers to achieve significant scale, expanding open access across thousands of journals. Building on [OASPA's recommended practices on financial and workflow barriers](#), publishers often implement waivers and are experimenting with tiered pricing for researchers from low-resource settings. However, [accessibility gaps persist](#) due to lack of awareness and limited consistency in waiver mechanisms. [Transformative agreements](#) have also been reshaping the publishing ecosystem. According to a [Jisc report](#) focusing on the UK landscape, such arrangements drove a 900% increase in articles published under transformative agreements between 2018-2022, as participating institutions grew from one to 38. Savings of over £16.7m (\$22m) were generated in the first year alone when compared to the previous year's expenditure. At the same time, this success was not without unintended consequences:

"Although the levels of Open articles in 2022 are similar (UK: 50%; global: 46%), the UK has a considerably higher proportion of Hybrid articles (UK: 21%; global: 10%)." [Brayman et al., 2024](#)

The scholarly community also continues to develop models where neither reading nor publishing require payment. These models are often community-led and prioritise inclusivity from the outset rather than retrofitting it into commercial frameworks. As a result, they tend to adopt a [mix of strategies](#) to achieve financial sustainability, including institutional subsidies, library consortia funding, foundation grants, community donations, volunteer labour, cross-subsidisation from other revenue streams, tiered membership fees based on institutional size, endowment income and strategic partnerships with academic departments or scholarly societies.

Positive incentives and research cultures can help escape a vicious circle

The research assessment landscape, including requirements from funders, institutions and more, [shapes researcher behaviour profoundly](#). Current evaluation systems tend to incentivise publication quantity, potentially contributing to the current challenges in upholding high levels of research integrity in the published record. Additionally, the preference for publication in indexed, predominantly English-language journals creates patterns that work against the principles of participatory and epistemic openness. For example, today's evaluation systems are known to disadvantage researchers from non-English speaking regions, those working at less-resourced institutions and scholars using methodologies or formats that don't align with traditional publishing expectations (e.g. articles, books, chapters):

"Non-native English speakers, especially those of low English proficiency nationalities, are more likely to have their papers rejected by journals due to English writing, compared to native English speakers." [Amano et al., 2023](#)

Initiatives promoting various types of reform have emerged in response to these challenges: [CoARA \(Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment\)](#), [DORA \(Declaration on Research Assessment\)](#), and the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#) are examples of coordinated efforts to transform evaluation practices toward more holistic, quality-focused approaches that recognise diverse contributions to knowledge.

The premise is that true openness requires not just removing paywalls but transforming the underlying incentive structures that determine whose voices and contributions are recognised and valued. However, the implementation of the principles proposed by these initiatives involves navigating institutional constraints, entrenched metrics and stakeholder interests, meaning that change will most likely continue to occur incrementally and over time.

Participatory openness

Enabling diverse contributions to and engagement in research from a wide range of actors

Furthering the transition to open access would benefit from increased alignment and collaboration

The global development of open access publishing has created a fundamental tension between standardised models (often commercial in nature) and diverse local ecosystems (often non-commercial): resolving this tension requires not harmonisation, but thoughtful integration that preserves regional innovations and enables authentic participation.

The open access approaches taken across [Latin America](#) and in [Indonesia](#) can be used to illustrate the above. These mature publishing ecosystems focus on free access to both authors and readers and mainly cover local languages, with this latter feature meaning that, for example, they are frequently [excluded from major bibliometric databases](#). This creates a false impression of Global North dominance in scholarly communication and makes potentially valuable contributions in non-English languages functionally invisible beyond their national or regional context. Bibliometric databases are making progress in enhancing the indexing of outputs in non-English languages, with [OpenAlex](#) showing particularly high proportions of these as well as including more diverse output formats. Overall, increased representation of a variety of languages, outputs and infrastructures would contribute to pursuing greater levels of openness and participation. To amplify diverse voices and approaches to open scholarship, greater levels of integration and collaboration between commercial and non-commercial publishing infrastructures would also be beneficial. Importantly, this is not an abstract conversation, and there are cases that showcase how the traditional dichotomy between commercial and non-commercial actors can be overcome. For example, [Open Research Africa](#) is an open access community platform supported by African funders and scientific organisations and delivered through F1000's infrastructure. With a slightly different focus, the [Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics \(SCOAP³\)](#) is a partnership between libraries, funding agencies and

research centres in 44 countries, regions or territories and three intergovernmental organisations and leading publishers to convert key journals in the field of High-Energy Physics to Open Access at no cost for authors. Today, initiatives like Open Research Africa and SCOAP³ are relatively small-scale compared to the global publishing enterprise, but they do demonstrate that finding consensus on mutually beneficial openness objectives across commercial and non-commercial actors is possible.

Ultimately, achieving a more equitable and sustainable open access ecosystem requires a shift in mindset - from viewing diversity (in languages, output types, policy landscapes and more) as an obstacle to treating it as an asset. Rather than seeking uniformity (e.g. a focus on economies of scale and efficiencies), we argue that it would be beneficial to embrace models that reflect the plurality of scholarly communication (e.g. pursuing greater levels of integration and mutual support).

Greater levels of digital sovereignty could enable broader participation in open sharing

An emerging challenge in the pursuit of participatory openness is the question of [digital sovereignty](#) in scholarly publishing infrastructure. While much attention has focused on who pays for open access, less consideration has been given to who controls the underlying technological systems that enable open scholarship. The concentration of publishing platforms, discovery tools and research metrics in the hands of a small number of entities creates inherent limitations on true participatory openness. Communities with distinct needs and perspectives, as well as traditions, often find themselves dependent on infrastructure that does not authentically represent them and has not been designed to [support and bridge the gap between diverse knowledge ecosystems](#). The result is a form of infrastructural lock-in that can perpetuate existing power imbalances even while rates of openness appear to be advancing at the surface level.

Epistemic openness

Broadening our understanding of what is valid and valuable knowledge

Embracing diverse knowledge systems strengthens scholarship and leads to positive social outcomes

Epistemic openness functions as essential connective tissue between scientific and participatory forms of openness. While scientific openness focuses on making research outputs widely available and participatory openness emphasises who can contribute, epistemic openness addresses the fundamental question of what knowledge is considered valid and valuable in the first place. Without epistemic openness, the other forms remain limited in their transformative potential.

"Far from constituting an obstacle to the implementation of open science, consideration of epistemic diversity can help realise the aspirations of the open science movement." [Leonelli, 2022](#)

The case for epistemic openness is not that anything goes. Rather, that the merits of different claims need to be tested, and some can then be recognised as having greater validity, even if uncertainty remains. Without this foundation, scientific openness might simply amplify dominant Western knowledge systems while marginalising others. Indeed, open access alone doesn't address deeper issues of epistemic injustice and exclusion.

While greater levels of open access publishing can make content more easily available and remove financial barriers for readers, this does not automatically correct for:

- historical power imbalances that determine whose knowledge is considered legitimate or valuable in the first place;
- language barriers that privilege English-language scholarship;
- digital divides in infrastructure and internet access that limit who can participate;
- academic cultural norms and citation practices that reinforce existing hierarchies; and
- the dominance of Western epistemological frameworks that may marginalise other knowledge systems.

Furthermore, by recognising diverse knowledge systems as valid and valuable, epistemic openness creates the conditions necessary for meaningful participation from previously excluded or marginalised communities. Pinfield observes that "participation in science should be open to people from low- and middle-income countries, just as much as high-income countries", but also that this participation must be on the basis of epistemological equality, not assimilation.

Furthermore, we need to recognise that knowledge production is inherently political and shaped by social contexts. In other words, we need not just access to knowledge, but to more significantly transform how knowledge is created, validated, shared and valued. In the context of existing publishing mechanisms, this could mean addressing representation challenges across editorial boards, peer review processes, research funding decisions and academic institutions.

The above means creating spaces where diverse epistemologies can flourish without being filtered through Western academic conventions, developing multilingual knowledge platforms that don't privilege English as the lingua franca of scholarship and building new customs that recognise community-based knowledge (e.g. oral traditions). It requires moving beyond a model that sees knowledge as a product to be distributed and towards understanding knowledge as an ongoing, collective process of sense-making across cultural, geographic and disciplinary boundaries.

Finally, we highlight that drawing upon multiple knowledge types (indigenous, local, science-based) is known to strengthen the evidence base for policy advice and decision-making. This indicates that a focus on epistemic openness is not only an abstract point and has demonstrated benefits. For example, growing evidence shows fruitful engagement between conventional scientific knowledge and indigenous knowledge systems in fields like land management and sustainable agriculture.

Epistemic openness

Broadening our understanding of what is valid and valuable knowledge

Ever more complex challenges will require new forms of inter- and trans-disciplinarity

Today's complex and 'wicked' problems can rarely be solved by individual disciplines. Open access can, in principle, play a significant role in making research findings available across disciplines, so that they may be used by any interested audiences. However, the picture is significantly complicated by the fact that open access adoption varies significantly by discipline and output type (e.g. articles vs long-form outputs, as discussed in previous pages), meaning that crossing boundaries can be difficult in practice.

Additionally, the current publishing system does not easily accommodate research outputs that go beyond articles, chapters, books or monographs formats. For example, non-text outputs in the form of visual media, exhibitions or performances are only beginning to be shared via open access, partly due to difficulties in capturing, documenting and preserving them in a way suitable for dissemination and further reuse.

The evolution toward more inclusive knowledge systems represents a significant opportunity for enriching scientific inquiry. As global challenges grow more complex, the engagement of diverse stakeholders and knowledge holders becomes not just beneficial but essential for developing robust solutions that are appropriate to a given context. This collaborative approach recognises that scientific knowledge gains depth and relevance when co-developed with broader society:

“Open science calls for engagement of stakeholders beyond the scientific community. Openness to varied sources of knowledge, such as Indigenous and local knowledge systems and citizen science, broadens and diversifies information for everyone.” [UNESCO, 2022](#)

Open access can be seen not just as a means of distributing academic outputs, but as an enabler of knowledge co-creation and as a tool for connecting diverse epistemologies and communities.

Innovation in content validation is needed to welcome more diverse forms of knowledge

New platforms are exploring innovative approaches beyond the journal model, testing the feasibility of open sharing of preprints, peer review reports and other research objects like research data or code. These initiatives represent a first step in reimagining scholarly communication and validation processes in a way that accommodates greater diversity of thought and methodology. This includes platforms that support open access micro-publications (e.g. [Octopus](#), [ResearchEquals](#)) with virtually no limitation on what can be posted and attributed a digital object identifier (DOI). The evolution of these platforms reflects a growing recognition that conventional publishing systems can create artificial constraints (e.g. length, formatting requirements) that may unintentionally exclude valuable contributions from the scholarly discourse. Furthermore, these emerging platforms are beginning to challenge the temporal rigidity of traditional publishing models. Rather than treating knowledge validation as a discrete event occurring at a fixed point in time (acceptance or rejection), they can enable ongoing engagement with research objects, allowing knowledge claims to evolve through continuous community interaction.

This, however, is only part of the picture. To truly welcome epistemic openness, we will need to consider expanding the current peer-review system to assess, validate and present diverse forms of knowledge. This requires us to consider evaluation frameworks that recognise by design that multiple valid ways of knowing exist, each with their own internal coherence and standards of evidence. Following this thinking, a broadening of how published works are validated would require technical features that enable the reader to see how different knowledge claims have been assessed and in which context. In simpler terms, we are referring to the need to evaluate knowledge not just based on content but also in relation to community needs, values and historical context.

Final remarks

The path towards equitable global open access requires us to move beyond today's norms and metrics and embrace a more nuanced understanding of openness. Here, we raise questions for the open access community.

The transition to open access would benefit from not only making more content freely available, but also from fundamentally reconsidering who participates in knowledge creation and what forms of knowledge we value. This means developing sustainable business models that work across diverse contexts, creating and integrating infrastructures that support multilingual scholarship and designing validation systems that recognise knowledge beyond Western paradigms. The challenge ahead is not merely technical or financial, but cultural, which requires us to reimagine scholarly communication as an inclusive ecosystem rather than a one-size-fits-all approach.

Moving forward, we invite all stakeholders - publishers, libraries, funders, researchers and knowledge holders of all kinds - to contribute to this 'different conversation' about open access. Over the coming years, we seek to develop approaches that balance standardisation with diversity, efficiency with equity and fixed notions of scholarship with diverse forms of knowledge sharing. The next phase of the open access movement must embrace a more holistic vision of openness: we wish to promote a transition towards a scholarly communication system that serves the global community equitably and amplifies and connects diverse voices and ways of thinking.

At a time when the open access transition appears to be slowing down and political and budget uncertainties increase complexity in our sector, we think it is important to pause and collectively consider what our future goals should be and how these could be funded sustainably. The core questions we wish to explore with the scholarly publishing community are as follows:

How can we translate the principles of scientific, participatory and epistemic openness into concrete terms during negotiations between stakeholders (publishers, libraries, funders, researchers)? What practical frameworks or tools would help bridge the gap between aspirational ideals and actionable agreements that effectively advance equitable open access?

To explore the above, we propose to discuss the following aspects in our workshops and online survey:

- **Beyond metrics:** If we move beyond simply counting the percentage of open access publications, what alternative indicators would better reflect truly equitable and inclusive progress towards open access?
- **Power dynamics:** What specific economic and institutional power dynamics currently block progress toward equitable open access, and how might these be addressed?
- **Digital sovereignty:** What concrete steps can we take to ensure that the global infrastructure supporting open access integrates diverse epistemologies rather than reinforcing existing power imbalances? How should these systems be governed?
- **Language and inclusion:** What would a truly multilingual scholarly ecosystem look like, and what structural changes would be required to ensure that language choice doesn't determine a work's impact or visibility?
- **Business models:** How can we improve existing business models to address inequities, and how do we ensure that models we have yet to imagine better serve the principles of scientific, participatory and epistemic openness?

Get in touch

About OASPA

Representing a diverse community of organisations engaged in open scholarship, OASPA works to encourage and enable open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs. We are committed to our mission of developing and disseminating solutions that advance open access and ensuring a diverse, vibrant, and healthy open access community.

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About Research Consulting

Research Consulting is a mission-driven research and scholarly communication consultancy, working with national and international organisations to help them make the most of their research processes and findings. We are active participants in the research ecosystem, and our work covers all aspects of the research life-cycle, including policy, funding, management, publishing and knowledge exchange.

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